

PRAGMATIC FUNCTION OF METAPHOR IN POLITICAL DISCOURSE

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6601737>

Anvarov Abdulkhamid Akmaljon o'gli
Uzbekistan State World Language University,
Linguistic faculty (MA)

Annotation: *This thesis deals with the pragmatic function of metaphor in political discourse. The variants of pragmatic metaphors are given with some examples to reveal the topic and explain.*

Key words: *metaphor, discourse, political, variant, usage*

Annotatsiya: *Bu tezis siyosiy nutqda metaforaning pragmatik vazifasini ko'rib chiqadi. Mavzuni ochish va tushuntirish uchun pragmatik metafora variantlari bir necha misollar bilan berilgan.*

Tayanch so'zlar: *metafora, nutq, siyosiy, variant, qo'llanish*

Metaphor is a powerful conversion tool that exists in the mind of the political world's addressee, pushing him to take specific actions, and its construction is required for the sender's emotional condition. The following are some examples of pragmatic metaphors: 1) *Incentive variant*; 2) *Argumentative variant*; 3) *Emotive variant*.

In the incentive variant the utilization of metaphor boosts the effectiveness of encouraging citizens to participate in political activities. For instance, a metaphorical request to "Come to a decisive battle with the enemy" is regarded very differently than a simple request to vote or join in demonstrations, even though in this situation the metaphorical battle is considered as a part of the elections or demonstrations.

Example: Snubbed Republican candidates embrace 'Happy Hour Debate' "...A vast majority of Republican voters, never mind Americans, still don't know who I am," Fiorina, the former Hewlett-Packard chief executive, said on MSNBC's "Morning Joe" Wednesday. "You have a long way to go here. It's a long race. And I'll look forward to the 'happy hour' debate..." [2].

In the argumentative variant, in political speech in order to influence the recipient's political opinions or beliefs, metaphorical reasoning [1] which stated by A. N. Baranov, is frequently utilized. At the first stage of the argumentation, metaphor provides access to the knowledge of a shared communicant, establishing a kind of common platform on which your point of view can be easily

expressed. For example, the argument that "the earth is the mother, and the mother cannot be sold" is frequently used by opponents of land sales which leads to the conclusion that selling the earth is impossible. The first part of this statement offers a common judgment for the Russian consciousness metaphor, which is also represented in the second part of the utterance (if not to regard the word mother as a metaphor). As a result, a special analysis is required for the sophisticated nature of justification which is not intended for all listeners.

Example from Barack Obama's speech on Iraq: "...Imagine, for a moment, what we could have done in those days, and months, and years after 9/11. We could have deployed the full force of American power to hunt down and destroy Osama bin Laden, Al Qaida, the Taliban, and all of the terrorists responsible for 9/11, while supporting real security in Afghanistan. We could have secured loose nuclear materials around the world, and updated a 20th century non-proliferation framework to meet the challenges of the 21st. We could have invested hundreds of billions of dollars in alternative sources of energy to grow our economy, save our planet, and end the tyranny of oil. We could have strengthened old alliances, formed new partnerships, and renewed international institutions to advance peace and prosperity. We could have called on a new generation to step into the strong currents of history, and to serve their country as troops and teachers, Peace Corps volunteers and police officers. We could have secured our homeland - investing in sophisticated new protection for our ports, our trains and our power plants. We could have rebuilt our roads and bridges, laid down new rail and broadband and electricity systems, and made college affordable for every American to strengthen our ability to compete [3].

We could have done that..." People who are affected by metaphorical reasoning are far more effective than others. In other circumstances, metaphorical arguments serve as a valuable addition to rational or emotive arguments.

In the emotional variant, a metaphor is frequently used to impact on the recipient's emotional-volitional domain and establish a corresponding relationship with the facts.

Example on the issue discussed (Campaign Policy Speech on Iraq, delivered 15 July 2008, Ronald Reagan Building, Washington, D.C.): "...The challenge facing the greatest generation of Americans - the generation that had vanquished fascism on the battlefield -- was how to contain this threat while extending freedom's frontiers. Leaders like Truman and Acheson, Kennan and Marshall, knew that there was no single decisive blow that could be struck for freedom.

We needed a new overarching strategy to meet the challenges of a new and dangerous world. ...”

Such metaphors are created primarily to transfer your current reader's emotional attitude toward the notion of source which implies acquiring the word's core meaning on the concept that is conceptualized in the metaphor. As a result, the natural attitude of every man toward an extremely hazardous contagious disease is applied to the attitude of ideological theory and practice through the use of metaphor.

USED LITERATURE:

1. Baranov A. N. The political metaphor of a journalistic text: The possibilities of linguistic monitoring // The language of mass media as an object of interdisciplinary research. Moscow, 2001.

2. <https://www.yahoo.com/politics/snubbed-republican-candidates-embrace-happy-hour-125938621586.html>

3. www.americanrhetoric.com/speeches/barackobama/barackobamairaquarreaganbuilding.htm